

PROCESSES OF FERTILIZER IN GROWING OF MULBERRY SEEDLINGS AND SEEDLINGS ON FARMS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6945095>

Roziev Alisher

Doctoral student of Tashkent State Agrarian University

Khaknazarova Umida

Master degree of Tashkent State Agrarian University, 1st year

Ochilova Mumtozbegin –

Student of Tashkent State Agrarian University

Annotation: *The most economically important part of the mulberry tree is the leaf, which is the silkworm's only food. Mulberry leaves contain nutrients that fully satisfy the needs of the silkworm - sugar, protein, fat, water, enzymes and various vitamins. As soon as the silkworm seed comes to life, it feeds on the mulberry leaf and eventually spins a cocoon. Therefore, the more mulberry leaves, the more worms can be fed and the more cocoons can be produced.*

Key words: *farming, cocooning, variety, hybrid, seedling, seedling, mulberry, seed, branch, leaf, fertile, productivity, environmental factors, fertilizers, enzymes, vitamins.*

In order to develop and implement the necessary measures for the comprehensive development of the cocoon industry, in accordance with the decision, improvement of the primary cocoon processing system, modern methods of quality management, wide introduction of popular types and designs of the finished product, its certification and standardization in accordance with international requirements, higher education special attention was paid to the development of proposals for the training of personnel for the cocoon industry in the institutions..

The main purpose of growing mulberry seedlings is to grow two-year-old hybrids for bushy mulberries and row mulberries, as well as grafted seedlings for grafting. Mulberry seed germination and seedling growth depend on soil, climate, and level of care, among other factors. Only if these meet the needs of the plant, it will grow well, the amount of sprouts grown per unit area will increase and its quality will be good.

In the southern and middle climatic regions of Uzbekistan, seedlings are grown for one year. To grow a one-year-old seedling, the seeds

prepared last year are sown, and the newly prepared seeds are sown in summer or autumn. To grow one and a half-year-old seedlings, the seeds prepared this year are sown in the summer, and the seedlings are left in the field for the second year.

It is possible to grow seedlings that meet the sample requirements only when the seed is planted and grown in the above periods.

The peculiarity of growing mulberry from seeds is that its germination and flowering are very slow in the first half of the growing season and require a lot of moisture. Because of this, many weeds grow in the nursery. Taking this into account, it is necessary to choose a site with less grass for the nursery.

The land freed from alfalfa is also very fertile. But it is not suitable to sow mulberry seeds on such land in the first year. Because alfalfa and weeds, whose roots have not yet dried up, will sprout in the field. As a result, a lot of work is spent on planting seedlings. In this case, many sprouts may die. In the first year, crops (cotton, potato, corn, sorghum, beetroot, etc.) that can be cut between rows should be planted on the land freed from alfalfa, weeded, and mulberry seeds should be sown in the second year.

Lands with heavy soil, strong and moderate salinity, near seepage waters, and where blue-worms, weevils, weevils and other harmful insects live are not suitable for nursery.

After harvesting the previous crops on the selected land for sowing mulberry seeds, the remaining stems and roots are attached to the T-40, T-548, T-70 S tractors PAS - 5-25 A garden plow-thresher /shallow plowing/, GJ uprooter or GUM, KC-4M is cleaned with the help of the stem pile machines. Autumn plowing is plowed evenly at a depth of 35-40 cm with a rotary plow no later than November 10. Before plowing, it is necessary to apply 150-200 kg of superphosphate and 5-10 tons of manure per hectare. If the soil is too dry, water is given to the field before plowing. 700-1000 m³ of water is poured per hectare of non-saline lands, and the amount of water given to saline lands is determined according to the salinity level of the soil. The ground is leveled well before plowing. After plowing in the fall, the lands that have been watered or washed with salt should be softened with a chisel and plowed in early spring, after the soil has loosened. If the land is not plowed in the fall for some reason, it is plowed at a depth of 28-30 cm and successively plowed.

Fast and uniform harvesting of lawns, growing many and quality seedlings per unit of area depends on correct determination of the amount of sowing seeds and early preparation for sowing.

The amount of seed planting depends on several factors, including: the number of seedlings grown per unit area according to the plan, the planting technique, the level of maintenance agrotechnics, the natural and climatic conditions of the place, and the ratio of seed germination under laboratory conditions to the degree of germination under field conditions.

Among the above factors, in determining the amount of planting in practical terms, the percentage of purity and germination of the seed, that is, its economic value, is of great importance.

To accelerate the germination of the seed, it is placed in bags made of gauze and soaked for 3 nights in running water or in a barrel or bowl where the water is changed 1-2 times every day. If the seeds are sown by machines, they are dried in the shade until they are ready for sowing, and there is no need for drying when sown by hand.

Sowing the seed in the soil is determined depending on the soil-climate and weather conditions of this or that region. It is planted in the southern regions of Uzbekistan from the end of March to the middle of April, in the regions with average climate from the second half to the end of April, in the northern regions from the end of According to R.Yu. Zverova's experience in the conditions of Tashkent region, when the temperature of the soil at the depth (0-5 cm) of the seed sown in the field is 10-11 $^{\circ}$ C, in 15-17 days, in 15-17 $^{\circ}$ C in 10-14 days, in 18-22 $^{\circ}$ C in 5 - bruised in 8 days. Such temperature in the soil corresponded to April 15-28, April 29-May 4, and May 6-14 in the years of the experiment (1965-1967). This author states that when the soil temperature is 18-22 $^{\circ}$ C and the humidity is 19-22%, the sown seed germinates quickly (6-10) days. Growth continues rapidly, and most seedlings meet the standard requirement.

According to M.Kuliyev, in the conditions of Turkmenistan, sprouts from mulberry seeds sown on April 16 were 22.7-42.5% more and of better quality than those sown on April 26 and May 16.

When the seed is sown, the temperature in the soil layer should be above +15 $^{\circ}$ C. It is necessary to sow freshly prepared seeds in the summer, as early as possible / no later than the end of May or the first half of June. In the southern regions, almost standard seedlings can be grown from seeds sown in summer until autumn. But in the regions with a medium climate and in the north, the sprouts grown from the seeds sown at this time are left for the second year to meet the standard requirements and are grown.

The ability to sow mulberry seeds in autumn was discovered by M. in Ukraine in 1930-1931. Filkov and in 1958 in Uzbekistan A.S. The Emelyanovs

tried it and got a positive result. The advantage of sowing seeds in the fall has been proven in practice since the 70s. For example, R. Abdullaev planted mulberry seeds in September, November and February 1970 in the experimental farm of the Central Asian Research Institute of Sericulture, and spread 1-2 cm of rotted manure on top of the bush. The lawns of the fields sown in November grew very well next year, 1 million 93 thousand seedlings were grown per hectare. The number of sprouts from seeds sown in September and February was 522-604 thousand, respectively. Similar in Khorezm region S. When mulberry seeds were sown in the Urgench mulberry nursery headed by Mahmudov on November 27, 1973, May 6 and 20, 1974, 1,20,000, 930,000 and 682,000 per hectare were sown in the periods 1-2-3 respectively, i.e., from the seeds sown in autumn, in summer (on May 6) compared to 90 thousand more seedlings were grown. That is, 65-45% standard sprouts were obtained from the seeds sown in the first and second period, respectively. All the sprouts that sprouted from the seeds sown in the summer (May 20) did not grow until autumn.

According to the experiments carried out by Yu. Miralimov, R. Sodikov and Kh. Beknazarov in Toshnet, Kashkadarya and Surkhondarya regions, mulberry seed seedlings sown in October and November grew faster compared to those in the field, and a large number of standard and even high quality seedlings were grown. Therefore, in the conditions of Uzbekistan, mulberry seeds can be sown in autumn, in addition to summer.

Cultivation and rotation of mulberry seedlings in the nursery

Young lawns need more moisture during the initial growth period. It is necessary to keep the tops of the bushes moist until the sprouts sprout. For this, every 3-4 days after the seeds turn blue, until 2-3 leaves appear, every 4-6 days until 5-6 leaves appear, every 6-8 days until 7-8 leaves appear, and from the second half of the growing season (summer). watered every 10-12 days. Watering is stopped at the end of August or the beginning of September so that the sprouts can ripen well before the frost.

If the seed is sown in the garden, it will sprout in 10-15 days, depending on the temperature of the soil, and in 7-8 days in summer. Seeds sown in the fall will sprout next year. At this time, the bushes are covered with weeds, they need to be weeded often. Weeds can appear even before the mulberry lawns emerge. In this case, it is necessary to mow the grass without waiting for the emergence of grass. Later, depending on the emergence of the grass, it is transplanted once every 18-22 days, 3-5 times in total.

It is advisable to use the drug "Edil" recommended by the Central Asian Scientific Research Institute of Sericulture for the fight against weeds..

For the good growth of seedlings, their thinning to the required level is also of great importance. When they have 4-5 leaves, each plant is thinned, leaving 2-3 cm between them. In order to make it easier to plant and harvest, the area of the field is first watered.

For the good growth of seedlings, their thinning to the required level is also of great importance. When they have 4-5 leaves, each plant is thinned, leaving 2-3 cm between them. In order to make it easier to plant and harvest, the area of the field is first watered.

Organic and mineral fertilizers are added to seedlings to make them grow stronger and to increase the number of standard seedlings per hectare. The amount and time of application of fertilizer is determined by the soil conditions of each region and the type of crop grown there before sowing.

Caring for mulberry seedlings.

Watering mulberry seedlings.

Growth of young seedlings.

According to the experiments conducted by M. No'monov (1968) in the Fergana Valley and Kh. Ubaykho'jaev (1969-1970) on the healthy soil of

the Tashkent region and L. Husniddinova (1972-1975) on the light sandy soil of the Chorjoi region, ¼ of the phosphorus fertilizer is mixed with mulberry seeds. grasses grew well when mixed and sprinkled on the ground and buried with 1-2 cm of soil. The stem of the seedling was strong and ripened well by autumn, I-II standard sprouts made up 80-85%. 700-800 thousand standard seedlings were grown per hectare, and the economic efficiency was equal to 2820 soums per hectare.

Organic fertilizers are given in autumn or spring before plowing the land, and mineral fertilizers are given during the growth of seedlings. The Central Asian Research Institute of Sericulture recommends the following amount when fertilizing seedlings. (Table 1)

Table 1.

Amount and duration of fertilizer for seedlings

Fertilizer type and annual quantity	Before sowing the seed	When 3-4 leaves appear on the sprout	A month after the appearance of 3-4 leaves on the seedling
10 t of manure + 60 kg of nitrogen + 60 kg of phosphorus fertilizer	7 t of manure + 30-45 kg of phosphorus fertilizer	30-45 kg nitrogen + 15-22 kg phosphorus fertilizer	30-45 kg nitrogen + 15-22 kg phosphorus fertilizer
120-180 kg of phosphorus fertilizer in the absence of manure	30-45 kg Phosphorous fertilizer	60-90 kg nitrogen + 15-22 kg phosphorus fertilizer	60-90 kg nitrogen + 15-22 kg phosphorus fertilizer

Note: The rest of the rotted manure is spread over the bushes after planting the mulberry seeds.

Mineral fertilizers are finely ground and placed in a tractor-mounted fertilizer 8-10 cm away from the seedling row and 10-15 cm deep into the soil. It is recommended to take the amount of mineral fertilizers at the expense of pure nutrients. Because, in addition to pure nutrients, there are various mixtures in the fertilizer. For example, ammonium nitrate contains 33 to 35% pure nitrogen, ammonium sulfate contains 20% pure nitrogen, superphosphate contains 14 to 18% pure phosphorus, and potassium salt

contains 40 to 55% pure potassium. Therefore, it is necessary to correctly determine how much fertilizer is needed to give a certain amount of nutrients to the plant. For example, we need to add nitrogen to the calculation of net nutrients, and we have 34% ammonium nitrate. In this case, if we divide 120 by 34 and multiply the result by 100 ($120:34 \times 100 = 353$), we get the amount of ammonium nitrate that needs to be multiplied by one. Therefore, 353 kg of ammonium nitrate should be used. Another example. 60 kg of pure phosphorus should be applied to each hectare of nursery, and we have 18% superphosphate. In this case, $60:18 \times 100 = 330$ kg of superphosphate should be applied.

REFERENCES USED:

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoev "Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of every leader's activity." Tashkent - "Uzbekistan" publishing house, 2017.
2. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2017 on measures to organize the activities of the "Uzbekipaksanoat" association.
3. Order No. F-4881 of March 24, 2017 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further support the enterprises of the silk industry of the Republic".
4. I.A. Karimov "The concept of deepening democratic reforms and development of civil society in our country" Tashkent-"Uzbekistan"-2010. November 12.
5. I.A. Karimov "Ways and measures to eliminate the world financial and economic crisis in the conditions of Uzbekistan" Tashkent-"Uzbekistan"-2009.
6. I.A. Karimov "Towards deepening economic reforms in Uzbekistan" Tashkent "Uzbekistan"-1995.
7. I.A. Karimov "Agricultural development - the source of abundant life" Tashkent "spirituality" - 1998.
8. Abdullaev U A.-Tutchilik. Tashkent. "Mehnat" publishing house, 1991
9. Akhmedov N.A. Feeding period of mulberry silkworm. "Silk" magazine 1999, No. 1